

Plant Growth Parameters in Pea under Different Plant Densities

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Abstract

Pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) is belongs to the Leguminosae family and currently grown in most temperate regions of the world. The research was carried out between February and June 2022 in the Dicle University, Faculty of Agriculture, in Diyarbakır, Turkey. In the experiment, four different plant densities (40, 60, 80, 100 seeds per square meters) were used in the Utrillo pea cultivar. The experiment was carried out the randomized complete blocks design with three replications. Plant rows were harvested every 10 days 45 days after sowing for plant height, number of nodes, leaflets, leaves and stipules per plant and leaf area. Crop growth rate (CGR), relative growth rate (RGR), net assimilation rate (NAR), absolute growth rate (AGR), leaf area index (LAI), leaf area ratio (LAR), leaf area duration (LAD), specific leaf area (SLA), specific leaf weight (SLW) values were calculated. All traits were affected by plant density. The plant height varied between 28.50 and 34.83 cm, and plant height decreased as increased plant density. The number of stipules per plant ranged from 7.94 to 9.50, and dense plant densities increased the number of stipules per plant. The highest crop growth rate (CGR) values from 45 days to 85 days during growth season were in DAE 85 and in 80 seeds per m². The highest RGR value was in DAE 55 and in 100 seeds per m². The highest plant density, 100 seeds per m², was produce high value of leaf area index (LAI).

Keywords: *Pisum sativum* L., plant density, plant growth parameters

INTRODUCTION

Pea (*Pisum Sativum*) belong to the leguminosea family, is divided into two subspecies as garden and fodder peas. Peas are annual and can grow in cool and temperate areas. It is important for food products. Although they are quite rich in protein (22.9%), they are an important source of vitamins, amino acids, carbohydrates, minerals, phosphorus, iron and calcium (Bhagat et al., 2015). Rhizobium bacteria help to enrich the soil with nitrogen by fixing the free nitrogen in the air to the soil. it contributes to sustainable agriculture.

Pea is the most produced legume crop in the world after common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L) and chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L). World pea production in 2022 is 11.1 million tons (FAO, 2021). The highest production in the world is ranked as America, Europe, Asia and Africa. The production area in Turkey is quite limited (10961 hectare) (FAO, 2020). The limited sown area and production is mostly due to not among our eating habits of pea. This situation caused by people's eating habits has been tried to be changed with healthy eating habits in recent years. There is almost no pea cultivation in the agricultural areas of Turkey outside the Aegean and Marmara regions. It is reported by various researchers that it is possible to grow pea outside of these areas (Tan and Yolcu, 2021). In Turkey, efforts to increase the sown area and production of peas are continued.

Varieties belonging to garden and field pea can be cultivated in almost all regions of Turkey and are produced by the private and state seed sector and released. It is important to promote pea production in huge

agricultural lands, to develop varieties with wide adaptation and to define their cultivation technics for every agricultural region.

Plant densities per unit area are important traits for growth, development and yield. Plant density may vary depending on the plant traits like botanical and genetic structure and environmental conditions such as soil, temperature and humidity. Climatic changes during any period of the growing season, especially sharply increasing and decreasing air temperature or low precipitation, greatly affect plant growth depending on plant age (Hatfield et al., 2011).

Plant density can affect ground cover, competitive ability with weeds, soil evaporation, light interception and lodging. Also, it can affect vigor, height, branching and the number of podded of variety. Plant density is affected by seedbed conditions and soil moisture, sowing depth, sowing date, presence or absence of weeds and seasonal rainfall (Armstrong et al., 2008). Recommendations for optimum plant requirement differ widely from country to country, from variety to variety. Krizmanić et al., (2020) reported that the 100 to 150 plant m⁻² plant density may be more suitable for a pea grown in eastern Croatia. In South-East Poland, Gugala and Zarzecka (2009) recommend a sowing density of 125 plants per m². Under Mediterranean conditions, Yucel (2013) reported that 40 plants per m² are most appropriate, and an increase in the plant density wasn't lead to a significant increase in pea. In contrast, Bitew et al., (2014) in North Western Ethiopia and Prusiński and Borowska (2022) in Middle Europe revealed that inter row spacing and plant density had no significant effect on all growth.

Growth is defined as an irreversible increase in size and volume of plant accompanied by increase in dry weight. Development refers to the quality changes in plant parts for example- Formation of flowers and fruits, falling of leaves etc. Crop growth rate (CGR), Relative growth rate (RGR), net assimilation rate (NAR), leaf area index (LAI), leaf area duration (LAD), leaf area ratio (LAR), absolute growth rate (AGR,) specific leaf area (SLA), specific leaf weight (SLW) are a useful tool in studying the complex interactions between the plant growth and the environment (Benbi, 1994; Singh et al., 1996). Prusiński and Borowska (2022) reported that there was no significant impact of the planting density on LAI value. However, Podleśny (2009) showed wide row spacing was low the LAI value. This study aimed to examine the growth parameters of pea sowing in early spring at different plant densities.

MATERYAL METOD

The research was carried out in February-June 2022 in the Dicle University, Faculty of Agriculture, in Diyarbakır, Turkey.

The trial soil was sandy-clay textured. Its pH value (7.19) was neutral/slightly alkaline, very low in terms of salinity, amount of organic matter and phosphorus. Climate data for 2022 were given in Figure 1. The lowest temperature was in March (5.7 °C), and the highest temperature was in June (27.6 °C). Total precipitation was highest in March (63.8 mm). In general, it was observed that February was cold and dry, March was cold but rainy, April was quite dry, but May was rainy, hot and humid.

Figure 1. Temperature and rainfall for the growing season

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In the experiment, four different plant densities (40, 60, 80, 100 seeds per m²) per square meters were used in the Utrillo pea cultivar. The experiment was carried out in the randomized complete blocks design with three replications. The plots were arranged in 4 rows with a length of 4 m and 45 cm between rows. Seeds were sown by hand on February 9, 2022. Irrigation water was not supplied. Weed control was manual. 20 cm length of plant rows were harvested every 10 days 45 days after sowing. The roots of the harvested plants were washed, and their moisture was removed by paper. The leaves, stems and roots of the plants were separated, and their fresh weights were weighed. Leaf area was measured by Winfolia 2003 software. The plant samples were dried in an oven at 80 °C for 72 hours and their dry weights were weighed by precision scale.

The growth formulas were given below.

$$CGR = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{t_2 - t_1} \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1} \text{ (Watson, 1956).}$$

$$RGR = \frac{(\log_e W_2 - \log_e W_1)}{(t_2 - t_1)} \text{ g g}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1} \text{ (Williams, 1946).}$$

$$NAR = \frac{(W_2 - W_1)}{(t_2 - t_1)} \times \frac{(\log_e L_2 - \log_e L_1)}{(L_2 - L_1)} \text{ g g}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1} \text{ (Williams, 1946).}$$

$$AGR = \frac{h_2 - h_1}{t_2 - t_1} \text{ cm day}^{-1} \text{ (Benbi, 1994)}$$

$$SLW = \frac{\text{Leaf weight}}{\text{Leaf area}} \text{ g cm}^{-2} \text{ (Pearce et al., 1968).}$$

$$SLA = \frac{\text{Leaf area}}{\text{Leaf weight}} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ (Kvet et al., 1971).}$$

$$LAI = \frac{\text{Total leaf area of a plant}}{\text{Ground area occupied by the plant}} \text{ (Williams, 1946).}$$

$$LAR = \frac{\text{Leaf area per plant}}{\text{Plant dry weight}} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ (Radford, 1967).}$$

$$LAD = \frac{L_1 + L_2}{2} \times (t_2 - t_1) \text{ (Power et al., 1967).}$$

W₁= dry weight per unit area at t₁, W₂= dry weight per unit area at t₂, t₁= first sampling, t₂= second sampling, h₁= the plant height at t₁, h₂= the plant height at t₂, L₁ = LAI at the first stage, L₂ = LAI at the second stage. The data were analyzed in the JMP 14 PRO package program. The "Excell" program was used for the growth parameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of different plant densities on the growth and development of pea plants were investigated. The effects of different plant density on plant height, number of nodes per plant, number of leaflets per plant, number of leaves per plant, number of stipules per plant, leaf area was significant (Table 1).

Tablo 1: Pea plant parameters under different plant densities during all growth periods.

DAE	Plant height (cm)	Number of nodes per plant	Number of leaflets per plant	Number of leaves per plant	Number of stipules per plant	Leaf area (cm ²)
45	19,41 e	5,4 d	6,00 e	18,66 d	6,58 e	68,12 c
55	26,45 d	7,66 c	8,66 c	20,16 c	9,16 d	98,63 b
65	33,54 c	10,58 b	11,83 b	22,25 b	10,08 c	172,43 a
75	36,75 b	11,91 b	12,75 a	30,83 a	11,08 b	184,39 a
85	39,25 a	13,91 a	13,00 a	31,25 a	11,91 a	172,77a
95	37,33 b	14,16 a	7,33 d	12,50 e	3,41 f	27,15 d
LSD: 0,05	0,83 *	0,49*	0,41*	0,72*	0,23*	7,56*
Plant densities						
40	34,83 a	11,33 a	11,88 a	23,61 a	8,94 ab	152,25a
60	32,69 b	10,72 b	9,00 c	21,11 c	8,44 bc	78,58 c

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80	32,47 b	10,44 b	9,22 bc	22,44 b	7,94 c	130,08 b
100	28,50 c	9,94 c	9,61 b	23,27 a	9,50 a	121,43 b
LSD: 0,05	0,44*	0,18*	0,24*	0,25*	0,23*	5,13*
Variation Sources						
Plant densities	125,52*	6,04 *	31,83*	22,33*	8,0134*	17147,6*
Error	1,7627	0,31481	0,53704	0,5694	0,51389*	237,248
DAE	707,7*	146,2*	107,48*	638,72*	121,325*	51476,8**
Plant densities *	32,65*	1,637	7,85*	26,87*	3,70278*	2486,41*
DAE						
Error	4,074	1,483	1,0167	3,147	0,3250	343,7

Means in similar category with different alphabets differ significantly. 0<,0001*

The plant height varied between 28.50 and 34.83 cm, and plant height decreased as increased plant density. The highest plant height was in 40 seeds per m², and the lowest plant height was in 100 seeds per m². In the period from 45 DAE to 95 DAE, the highest plant height (39.25 cm) was in 80 DAE. Our study was not in agreement with the early research Singh et al. (2001) and Habbasha et al. (1996) reported that plant height increased in high plant density compared to low plant density, but Knott and Belcher (1998) reported that the increased amount of seed did not affect plant height.

The number of nodes per plant ranged from 9.94 to 11.33, and the plant density affected the number of nodes per plant. Number of nodes was increased as the plant density decreased, and the highest number of nodes was in 40 seeds per m². The number of DAE nodes was found to be statistically significant, and the number of nodes continued to increase in all growth and development periods.

The number of leaflets and leaves per plant were affected by plant densities, the number of leaflets and leaves per plant varied between 9.00 and 11.88, 21.11 and 23.6, respectively. The lowest number leaflets and leaves were determined in 60 seeds per m². Number of leaflets and leaves per plant increased until DAE 85 days, but these traits were decreased at DAE 95 days.

The number of stipules per plant ranged from 7.94 to 9.50, and dense plant densities increased the number of stipules per plant. The highest number of stipules per plant was in 100 seeds per m². The number of stipules per plant increased until DAE 85 days but decreased towards the end of the growing season.

Leaf area was affected by plant density, and ranged from 72.28 cm² to 152.25 cm². As the plant density decreased, the number of leaves increased, and the highest leaf area was in 40 seeds per m². Leaf area increased until DAE 75, and the lowest value reached in 95 days.

Crop growth rate (CGR), relative growth rate (RGR), net assimilation rate (NAR), absolute growth rate (AGR), leaf area index (LAI), leaf area ratio (LAR), leaf area duration (LAD), specific leaf area (SLA), specific leaf weight (SLW) values were given in figure 2,3,4,5.

Figure 1. Crop Growth Rate (CGR) and Relative Growth Rate (RGR) of pea under different plant densities

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The highest crop growth rate (CGR) values from 45 days to 85 days during growth season were in DAE 85 and in 80 seeds per m². Relative Growth Rate (RGR) was significant, and the highest RGR value was in DAE 55 with in the plant density 100 seeds per m². Low air temperature on the 45th and 55th days after sowing was caused to decline or slow down the crop growth (Fig.1). On the 75th day after sowing, there was a decrease in all plant densities except for 100 seeds per m² plant density due to the lack of precipitation, that was, drought.

Figure 2. Net Assimilation Rate (NAR) and Absolute Growth Rate (AGR) of pea under different plant densities

The highest net assimilation rate (NGR) and absolute growth rate (AGR) was in 80 seeds per m² and in DAE 85. The presence of cloudy and rainy weather in the experimental area between the 65th and 75th days after sowing slightly reduced the plant growth and development. Ozbakir et al. (2012) reported that decreasing temperature and light reduced the net assimilation rate. Oner and Sezer (2007) reported that increased temperature at low light and increased light intensity at high temperature caused a decrease in the net assimilation rate.

Figure 3. Leaf Area Ratio (LAR) and Leaf Area Index (LAI) of pea under different plant densities

Leaf area ratio (LAR) decreased as the number of days increased from DAE 45 days to DAE 95 as a result of the decrease in leaf to stem ratio. Leaf area index (LAI) was increase from 45 to 85 days, but it was decrease 85 days to 95 days. Towards the 95th day, this rate decreased due to the yellowing of the leaves and the absence of new leaves with the ripening of the crop. The highest plant density, 100 seeds per m², was produce high value of leaf area index (LAI) (Fig. 3). Prasad et al. (2012) and Khan (2000) determined that LAI and LAD decreased during the period from sowing to harvest.

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Figure 4. Leaf Area Duration (LAD) and Specific Leaf Area (SLA) of pea under different plant densities

Leaf area duration increase from 45 days to 75 days decreased from 75 days to 85 days. It was determined that the highest value was plant density 100 seeds per m² and in DAE 75 (Fig.4). Specific leaf area (SLA) decreased as the number of days increased from DAE 45 days to DAE 95 as a result of the decrease in leaf to stem ratio. The area of photosynthesis increased with plant growth. Leaf weight increased to the highest rate during flowering and podding stages. The specific leaf area ratio, which increases the rate of photosynthesis per plant, also increased. However, leaf area ratio decreased significantly towards plant maturation. Similarly, it was a significant effect of the mean monthly temperature and the total precipitation on pea growth during growing season.

Figure 5. Specific Leaf Weight (SLW) of pea under different plant densities

The plant growth parameters were affected by a number of factors such as temperature, solar radiation levels, water, nutrient needs, crop and variety. These factors affect leaf size and productivity, so the ability of plants to convert solar energy into economic growth. When the climate data were examined, February and March were cold, and April was no-rainy. Therefore, the plant emergence and flowering were delayed. The rainfall in May accelerated the vegetative development of the plant, increased the leaf area and increased in CGR, RGR, NAR, AGR and SLW. In addition, the period of increase in LAR, LAI, LAD and SLA coincided with May. However, decreases were observed in LAR, LAI, LAD and SLA during the period from DAE 45 to DAE 95 due to increasing temperatures, the highest LAI ratio was DAE 85 for plant density 100 seeds per m², and the highest LAD ratio was in DAE 75 and 100 seeds per m² (Fig. 2).

CONCLUSIONS

The effects of different plant density on the growth parameters of pea plants were investigated. It has been determined that climatic changes are very effective in plant growth, and CGR, AGR, NAR, SLW values increase in the period from planting to harvest. It was determined that the highest leaf area and plant height

were obtained from the plant density 40 seeds per m². CGR, AGR, NAR parameters reached the highest values of plant density 80 seeds per m².

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